

Spiro Heterocycles. Part-XIX. Synthesis and Insecticidal Activity of some New Fluorine-containing Spiro[4*H*-1-benzopyran-4,3'-[3*H*]-indole]-3-carbonitriles/ carboxyethylesters

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A number of fluorinated spiro[4*H*-1-benzopyran-4,3'-[3*H*]-indole]-3-carbonitriles/ carboxyethylesters have been synthesised and tested for their insecticidal activity against *Prodenia litura* and *Musca domestica*. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by elemental analysis, ir, pmr and mass spectral studies.

INDOLE nucleus has been found to be associated with diverse biological activities¹. Serotonin, an indole derivative is an important brain amine and plays a significant role as modulator of CNS neurochromal activity². Benzopyran derivatives are also found to be endowed with various biological activities like antiallergic³, insecticidal⁴ and anticoagulant⁵. The recent discovery of the spiro compound fredricamycin-A as an antitumor-antibiotic, the use of spiro[benzopyran-2,2'-indoles] for photochromatic effect and the fact that a number of alkaloids which are psychoactive are indole derivatives with a spiro system at position-3 of the indoline skeleton, prompted us to prepare compounds having indole and benzopyran moieties linked through a spiro atom. Further, fluorine was incorporated as this enhances biological activities⁶.

The present paper deals with the synthesis and insecticidal activity of some fluorine containing spiro[4*H*-1-benzopyran-4,3'-[3*H*]-indole]-3-carbonitriles/carboxyethylesters. Fluorinated indole-2,3-diones (1) were prepared by literature methods⁷. The reaction of indole-2,3-diones, with malononitrile/ethylcyanoacetate in presence of piperidine as catalyst, resulted in the formation of 3-dicyano/ carboethoxycyanomethyleneindole-2-ones (2),⁸ which when subjected to Michael reaction with cyclohexane-1,3-dione afforded the title compounds (3)⁸.

Results and Discussion

Spectral studies: In the ir spectra of compounds 3a-i, a doublet at 3 340 and 3 240 cm⁻¹ representing respectively, the 'free' asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching due to NH₂ group and two carbonyl absorptions at 1 700 and 1 665 cm⁻¹ are observed. A singlet near 3 100 cm⁻¹ (NH) in compounds 3a-c, 3e, 3f and 3i, near 2 200 cm⁻¹ (C≡N) in compounds 3a-d, 3g-i and an additional C=O absorption near 1 680 cm⁻¹ in compounds 3e and 3f are also observed. In the pmr spectra a singlet

Scheme 1

near δ 10.3 (NH₂) and a multiplet at δ 7.1-6.4 (ArH) are observed in all the cases. In compounds 3a-c and 3i three multiplets centered at δ 2.6, 2.2 and 1.9 corresponding to the protons on C-6, C-7 and C-8 respectively, of the benzopyran ring are observed. In compounds 3d-h a large number of peaks are observed in the region δ 1.5-2.4 due to CH₂NCH₂, CH₂OCH₂, COCH₃ or COOCH₂CH₃ and CH₂CH₂CH₂ of benzopyran ring. A singlet near δ 7.3 (NH) is also observed in 3a-c, 3e, 3f and 3i. In the ¹⁹F nmr spectra singlets for 5-F, 6-F and 4-CF₃ are observed at δ -112.01, -119.11 and -62.99 ppm respectively. Mass spectral studies further support their formation as molecular ion peaks (M⁺) at m/e 307 (3a), 325 (3b), 367 (3d), 384 (3e) and 375 (3i) correspond to their molecular weights.

Insecticidal activity: It was observed that the compounds are more active against *Prodenia* species as compared to *Musca* species, some of them showing even 100% activity against the former. In the case of *Prodenia* species, it is also observed that compounds 3a-d, possessing a CN substituent, are

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd. no.	X	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	H	H	ON	> 300	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃
3b	5-F	H	ON	274	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ FN ₃ O ₃
3c	6-F	H	ON	> 300	73	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ FN ₃ O ₃
3d	5-F	COCH ₃	ON	> 300	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ FN ₃ O ₄
3e	5-F	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	260	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ FN ₃ O ₃
3f	6-F	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	270	71	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ FN ₃ O ₃
3g	5-F	CH ₂ - N	ON	> 300	67	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ FN ₄ O ₄
3h	5-F	CH ₂ - N	ON	> 300	69	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ FN ₄ O ₃
3i	4-CF ₃	H	ON	> 300	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ F ₃ N ₃ O ₃

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

more active as compared to analogs having a COOC₂H₅ group. With *Musca* species, high activity of compounds 3c and 3f indicates that fluorination at position-6 enhances the activity. Highest activity is observed for 3d leading to the conclusion that N-acetylation also increases the activity in this case.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, pmr and ¹⁹F nmr spectra on a Jeol FX-90 Q spectrometer using TMS as internal reference for pmr and C₆H₆ as external reference for ¹⁹F nmr, and mass spectra on a MS-30 and MS-50 Kratos spectrometer.

5/6-Fluoro/4-trifluoromethylindole-2,3-diones (1) : The compounds were prepared by literature methods⁷ using the corresponding fluorinated anilines.

3-Dicyano/carboethoxycyanomethyleneindole-2-ones (2) : A mixture of 5/6-fluoro/4-trifluoromethylindole-2,3-dione (0.17 mol) and malononitrile/ethylcyanoacetate (0.17 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) containing piperidine (2–3 drops) as catalyst was refluxed for 3 h⁹. After being chilled overnight, the resulting solid was filtered, washed with ether (10 ml) and recrystallised from ethanol as violet needles.

Spiro[4H-1-benzopyran-4,3'-[3H]-indole]-3-carbonitriles/carboxyethyl esters (3) : A solution of 3-dicyano/carboethoxycyanomethyleneindole-2-one (0.01 mol) and cyclohexane-1,3-dione (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was treated with piperidine (2 drops) and was stirred at room temperature for 4 h⁹. After the removal of ethanol, the residual product was rinsed with dichloromethane and the insoluble solid recrystallised from ethanol to give light coloured crystals, which were homogeneous on tlc (Table 1).

Evaluation of insecticidal activities : The insecticidal activity of six representative compounds (3a–f) was evaluated against the larvae of *Prodenia litura* (Tobacco caterpillar) and *Musca domestica* (adult house-fly).

For activity against *Prodenia* species leaf dip method was used. A 1000 ppm solution of the compound was prepared in 5% ethanol. Fresh castor leaves were taken, each being dipped in the chemical (1000 ppm) and allowed to dry. The leaves were put in the petri plates and 20 larvae of *Prodenia* sp. were released into each one of them. A control was also taken. The larvae were left undisturbed under laboratory conditions and observations were taken after 20 h of exposure.

For activity against *Musca* species, house-fly bait test was used. A 500 ppm solution of the compound in 5% ethanol with 10% sugar was prepared. A 40 ml of the chemical-bait solution was soaked in the absorbant cotton placed in the petri dish. A control was also taken. These petri dishes were placed in 1 cu ft mosquito net fly cage. The adult house-flies were released into each one of these cages and observations were taken after 20 h of exposure.

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